

RESULTS OF VERA APPLICATION TO THE AP1000[®] PWR STARTUP

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the application of the Virtual Environment for Reactor Applications, VERA, under development by the Consortium for Advanced Simulation of LWRs (CASL) to the core physics analysis of the AP1000 PWR.

The AP1000 PWR features an advanced first core with radial and axial heterogeneities which provides significant enhancements compared to traditional first cores, allowing best fuel usage and short transition to the equilibrium cycle with subsequent fuel reloads. These core advanced features can pose some challenges to the core physics tools making application of VERA to the AP1000 PWR first core especially relevant to qualify VERA performance.

This paper focuses on the qualification efforts at hot zero power conditions, where Monte-Carlo reference solutions have also been established. In particular, the paper focuses on the comparison of the predictions obtained with VERA for the four AP1000 units that recently started up with the measured values. It is shown that there is excellent agreement between VERA and the key reactor physics parameters measured during the AP1000 startup.

KEYWORDS: AP1000, CASL, VERA

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper describes the application of the Virtual Environment for Reactor Applications, VERA, under development by the Consortium for Advanced Simulation of LWRs (CASL), to the core physics analysis of the AP1000 PWR. The AP1000 PWR has a low-leakage 18-month cycle advanced first core [1] featuring five fuel regions with intra-assembly enrichment zoning and a combination of burnable absorbers: the Westinghouse Integral Fuel Burnable Absorber (IFBA) a ZrB₂ coating on the pellet surface, and the Wet Annular Burnable Absorber (WABA), an insert employed at selected guide thimble locations. The core loading pattern is depicted in Figure 1. Figure 1 also shows the assembly loading pattern for Region D fuel, featuring radial enrichment zoning (3 enrichments), 68 IFBA rods, 8 “long” and 4 “short” WABA inserts.

The long and short WABA inserts differ in the axial length (longer or shorter) of the poisoned-bearing region (see Figure 2), with the top plena and lower Zr spacer varying accordingly. Region E fuel assemblies are similarly characterized by enrichment zoning, IFBA rods and, when present, axially heterogeneous WABA inserts. Lower-enriched axial blankets are employed for Regions C, D and E; the blankets for the IFBA rods consist of annular fuel with a central void to accommodate He release from ^{10}B neutron absorptions in ZrB_2 . For the various fuel regions, Table 1 provides the average enrichment at the core mid-plane, the number of assemblies in the core (out of 157 total) pertaining to each region, the blanket enrichment when present and the burnable absorbers specification.

The AP1000 PWR operates following the MSHIMTM core control strategy, an advanced operational strategy that entails operation with multiple control rod banks inserted in the core, including light tungsten banks and standard Ag-In-Cd banks [2-3]. The control banks configuration is shown in Figure 3. The banks used for MSHIM maneuvers are the M-banks, typically the light tungsten banks MA through MD, with the AO bank used for controlling the axial power distribution.

The AP1000 PWR advanced core design and operational features make application of an advanced core simulator like VERA especially relevant for the analysis.

2. CODES EMPLOYED

The simulations performed for this analysis have been developed employing VERA [4]. VERA is an advanced package for reactor analysis which performs direct whole-core neutronic calculations coupled with sub-channel T/H feedback, thereby eliminating the inaccuracies involved in the traditional two-step process adopted for reactor analysis. The reactor core simulator of VERA, MPACT [5], provides an advanced pin-resolved transport capability within VERA. The key characteristics of the MPACT code include the subgroup method and the embedded self-shielding method (ESSM) for resonance treatment, depletion capability based on the ORIGEN [6] exponential matrix method, and a whole core solver with a 2-D/1-D synthesis method on the frame of a 3-D coarse mesh finite difference (CMFD) method for which axial and radial correction factors are obtained from 2-D method of characteristics (MOC) and 1-D Simplified PN. COBRA-TF (CTF) [7] is the T/H component of VERA. CTF is a quality controlled, state-of-the-art version of the COBRA-TF sub-channel thermal-hydraulic code. In VERA, CTF is directly coupled to MPACT and is executed in full for each neutronics-T/H feedback iteration until convergence is reached between the two codes. With these features, VERA provides direct and fully coupled solutions at the sub-channel level for T/H and intra-rod level for neutronics without requiring any homogenization, hence does not require application of approximate power/flux reconstruction techniques, like in typical industrial reactor physics toolkits.

Given the fresh fuel and uniform temperature conditions it has also been possible to establish Monte-Carlo Continuous Energy (CE) reference solutions for selected cases. In particular, the Monte-Carlo tool SHIFT has also been employed to model the AP1000 core for the startup simulations. SHIFT [8] is a general purpose radiation transport code that performs stochastic modeling of particle physics using the Monte Carlo method; it uses the Multiple-Set-Overlapping-Domain (MSOD) parallel scheme that allows full domain replication, domain decomposition, and domain decomposition with overlap and multiple sets.

Figure 1 AP1000 PWR First Core – Fuel Loading Pattern (Quarter Core Radial Map) and Region D Fuel Lattice Design (Quarter Assembly Radial Map)

Table 1 Fissile, IFBA and WABA Content for the AP1000 PWR First Core (“L”: Long WABA, “S”: Short-WABA, “I”: Intermediate WABA)

Region Identifier	Number of Assemblies	²³⁵ U Midplane	²³⁵ U Blanket	IFBA Rods	WABA Rods
A	16	0.740	Absent	0	0
B	49	1.580	Absent	0	0
C	28	3.200	1.580	0	0
D	36	3.776	3.200	68	8L+4S
E(1)	8	4.376	3.200	88	4I
E(2)	4	4.376	3.200	124	0
E(3)	16	4.376	3.200	124	8I

Figure 2 AP1000 PWR First Core – Fuel Axial Configuration

Figure 3. AP1000 PWR Control Banks Configuration (Quarter Core Radial Map)

3. RESULTS

An extensive set of simulations has been performed with VERA for the AP1000 PWR, with past results presented in [9-12]. The results presented here are focused on Hot Zero Power (HZP) simulations (e.g. HZP critical boron, Isothermal Temperature Coefficient (ITC) and rod worth), and namely on the

comparison between predicted values with the corresponding startup measured parameters at four AP1000 units that recently began commercial operation.

3.1. Main Modeling Assumptions

The results of the comparisons for each figure of merit are expressed as deltas between the predicted and measured value, indicating each of the four AP1000 units modeled as plant “A” through “D”. The typical settings used in standard PWR core calculations have been employed, and namely transport-corrected scattering (“TCP0”), 0.05 cm ray spacing, three radial rings per fuel pellet with eight azimuthal angles. The impact of refining some of these settings has been assessed as well with results to be presented later.

SHIFT calculations employed 25 million particles per generation for a total of 2,000 generations with 500 inactive cycles, resulting in an eigenvalue statistical uncertainty typically of 0.5 pcm.

Thermal expansion at hot zero power temperature has been assumed for all calculations. IFBA and U as-built values have been modeled on a per region basis. The natural ¹⁰B content of 19.90 a/o in B has been assumed.

The libraries used have been generated by the AMPX code system [13] based on ENDF/B-VII.0 CE cross section library for SHIFT (a continuous energy library has been used) and ENDF/B-VII.1 for MPACT (a 51-group cross-section library has been used).

3.2. HZP Critical Boron

Table 2 shows the delta in HZP critical boron for MPACT and SHIFT vs. the measured critical boron for each plant. As it can be seen, there is excellent agreement with the measured boron at the plants with both codes mildly underpredicting the critical boron, an average delta of -9 ppm with a standard deviation of 8 ppm for MPACT, and an average delta of -5 ppm with a standard deviation of 7 ppm for SHIFT. Note that while the behavior in the delta P-M critical boron for plant A, C and D is very consistent, plant B deviates from the observed trend.

Table 2 Delta in HZP Critical Boron Concentration for MPACT and SHIFT vs. Measurements

	MPACT Delta P-M (ppm)	SHIFT Delta P-M (ppm)
A	-13	-9
B	6	8
C	-14	-9
D	-14	-8
Avg.	-9	-5
Std. Dev.	8	7

3.3. Isothermal Temperature Coefficient

Table 3 shows the delta ITC predicted by MPACT and SHIFT vs. the measured ITC for each plant. It should be noted that the ITC simulation has been performed at the measured critical boron for the respective plant. While MPACT predicts the ITC with satisfactory accuracy, on average -0.21 pcm/F from the measurements with a standard deviation of 0.19, SHIFT mispredicts the ITC by nearly -1 pcm/F (only a single plant ITC has been calculated with SHIFT). The behavior from the SHIFT code, with respect to ITC calculations, is in line with past observations relative to the KENO code. This issue needs further investigation to understand the reason leading to this discrepancy.

Table 3 Delta in ITC for MPACT and SHIFT vs. Measurements

	MPACT Delta P-M (pcm/F)	SHIFT Delta P-M (pcm/F)
A	-0.27	
B	-0.46	
C	-0.19	
D	+0.07	-0.94
Avg Delta	-0.21	
Std Dev Delta	0.19	

3.4. Rod Worth

Table 4 shows the delta in rod worth for MPACT vs. the measured worth given both as delta pcm and delta % worth. There is remarkable accuracy in the predicted values across all plants and banks, with most of the banks predicted within 1% or 10 pcm accuracy.

Table 5 shows the delta in rod worth when P2 scattering is used instead of TCP0 and the delta in rod worth predicted by SHIFT vs. the measured rod worth for plant D. While the P2 scattering results only mildly improve the results, the agreement with the measured worth shown by the SHIFT code is outstanding.

Table 4 Delta in Rod Worth for MPACT vs. Measurements

Bank Name	A: delta pcm	B: delta pcm	C: delta pcm	D: delta pcm	A: delta %	B: delta %	C: delta %	D: delta %
MA	-1	-3	0	0	-0.5%	-1.2%	0.1%	-0.2%
MB	-2	-2	-4	-7	-1.2%	-1.1%	-1.7%	-3.5%
MC	-4	-8	-4	-10	-2.3%	-4.3%	-2.0%	-5.7%
MD	-3	-3	-2	-3	-1.5%	-1.3%	-0.7%	-1.4%
M1	15	11	6	5	2.3%	1.7%	1.0%	0.8%
M2	13	6	1	0	1.4%	0.7%	0.1%	0.0%
AO	52	14	-59	6	3.2%	0.9%	-3.8%	0.4%
S1	11	-1	34	-14	1.0%	-0.1%	3.1%	-1.3%
S2	29	23	7	-3	2.6%	2.1%	0.6%	-0.3%
S3	12	0	-4	-11	1.1%	0.0%	-0.4%	-1.0%
S4	4	5	3	-3	0.7%	0.9%	0.6%	-0.5%
Avg Delta	11	4	-2	-4	0.6%	-0.2%	-0.3%	-1.2%
Std Dev Delta	16	9	21	6	1.7%	1.7%	1.7%	1.8%

Table 5 Delta in Rod Worth for MPACT with TCP0 vs. P2 Scattering and Delta Rod Worth for SHIFT (Plant D)

Bank Name	MPACT TCP0 delta pcm	MPACT TCP0 delta %	MPACT P2 delta pcm	MPACT P2: delta %	SHIFT delta pcm	SHIFT delta %
MA	0	-0.2%	0	0.1%	0	0.0%
MB	-7	-3.5%	-6	-2.7%	-4	-1.8%
MC	-10	-5.7%	-9	-5.2%	-5	-2.9%
MD	-3	-1.4%	1	0.5%	1	0.4%
M1	5	0.8%	6	0.9%	6	0.9%
M2	0	0.0%	-3	-0.4%	2	0.3%
AO	6	0.4%	-2	-0.1%	1	0.0%
S1	-14	-1.3%	-9	-0.8%	-13	-1.3%
S2	-3	-0.3%	-8	-0.7%	-1	-0.1%
S3	-11	-1.0%	-4	-0.3%	-9	-0.8%
S4	-3	-0.5%	-5	-0.8%	1	0.2%
Avg Delta	-4	-1.2%	-3	-0.9%	-2	-0.5%
Std Dev Delta	6	1.8%	4	1.6%	5	1.1%

4. CONCLUSIONS

The results presented show excellent agreement in the MPACT and SHIFT predictions for the HZP critical boron concentration and rod worth for the AP1000 PWR. While the ITC predicted by MPACT shows satisfactory accuracy, SHIFT underpredicts the ITC by nearly 1 pcm/F, showing a recurring problem, to the authors' experience, with Monte Carlo tools in calculating this parameter.

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